
Chronic obstructive pulmonary condition (COPD) is a prevalent, preventable, and curable illness with persistent respiratory symptoms and airflow limitation**Moataz Dowaidar^{1,2}**¹Department of Bioengineering, King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran 31261, Saudi Arabia²Interdisciplinary Research Center for Hydrogen and Energy Storage (IRC-HES), King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran, 31261, Saudi Arabia.

Abstract: Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) research on chronic obstructive pulmonary condition (COPD) characterizes it as a prevalent, preventable, and curable illness with persistent respiratory symptoms and airflow limitation. Airway blockage resulting in dyspnoea and air trapping when exercising airflow restriction can be attributed to smoking, ambient tobacco smoke exposure, and the patient's TB history. COPD airflow restriction is largely caused by airway tightness, chronic bronchitis, or emphysema. Repeated inhalation of hazardous particles induces chronic inflammatory immune cell infiltration, tissue repair, and airway remodeling, resulting in a 4-to 40-fold increase in airway resistance and bronchiolar constriction. 20% of small airways are bronchi, with the rest being either bronchioles or alveolar ductal gaps. Flow restriction includes alveolar wall disintegration and alveolar support. The modifications worsen the rapid FEV1 fall and contribute to the airway obstruction seen in COPD. COPD, small airway disease (SAD), has been extensively studied. Inflammation, fibrosis, and destruction of bronchioles are all indications of this illness. Mixed pulmonary fibrosis and emphysema (CPFE). In fact, fibrosis appears to be involved in the obstruction of small airways.

RAGE participates in several intracellular processes by binding to several ligands. RAGE ligand interactions trigger downstream signaling pathways that have been associated with COPD and other disorders. Thus, inhibitors of RAGE and its signaling pathways also have been found to play a function in other disorders, which suggests that they might be used to treat COPD. There are currently no established biomarkers to diagnose COPD. COPD patients are shown to have altered RAGE and some of its ligands. Despite a lack of agreement on how smoking affects sRAGE levels, greater study is needed to discover whether or not this biomarker is stable. It was discovered that among the North Han Chinese, -429T > C is associated with COPD. COPD vulnerability is furthermore associated with the genetics of RAGE. To get a better diagnosis, population-based studies are needed. Finally, RAGE, AGE-RAGE, and sRAGE all impact COPD, and RAGE may be employed as a biomarker for diagnosis and management of COPD patients if more study supports this hypothesis.

1. Introduction

Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) studies describe chronic obstructive pulmonary condition (COPD) as a widespread, preventable, and curable disease with persistent respiratory symptoms and airflow restriction (1). COPD is characterized by a poorly reversible airway obstruction that results in air trapping and dyspnoea during exercise (2). Smoking, ambient tobacco smoke exposure, and the patient's TB history are the most prevalent causes of airflow restriction (2). Airflow limitation in COPD is mostly caused by

airway constriction, chronic bronchitis, emphysema, or a combination of these disorders (3). Continuous inhalation of toxic particulates triggers a cycle of chronic inflammatory immune cell infiltration, tissue repair, and airway remodelling in COPD patients, resulting in a 4–40-fold increase in resistance in small airways (less than 2 mm in diameter) and narrowing of terminal bronchioles (4). Bronchi make up around 20% of tiny airways under 2 mm in diameter, with the balance being bronchioles or alveolar ductal gaps (5). The breakdown of alveolar walls and alveolar support are two more aspects that contribute to airflow restriction (6). These alterations exacerbate the fast drop in forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV1) and contribute to airway obstruction in COPD. The major symptom of COPD, small airway disease (SAD), has been widely researched. Mucus clogging of tiny airways, inflammation, fibrosis, and destruction of tiny bronchioles are all symptoms of this condition. COPD is characterized by the loss of alveoli in the lung parenchyma rather than fibrosis, but in certain individuals, both disorders coexist, resulting in combined pulmonary fibrosis emphysema (CPFE). However, fibrosis appears to be a significant mechanism in the constriction of tiny airways (7).

Chronic inflammation, which involves the infiltration of numerous immune cells such as neutrophils and lymphocytes into the lung tissues and small airways, is another crucial factor for the development of COPD (8). Neutrophils are important cells in this process and are used as a measure of COPD severity in patients (9). Matrix metalloproteinases and other enzymes secreted by neutrophils and macrophages are implicated in alveolar degradation (8). Adaptive immunity kicks in as the illness progresses, resulting in increased quantities of B and T lymphocytes (TH1 and cytotoxic T cells) in the lungs, amplifying neutrophil-mediated inflammation (2). Because of its high incidence rate, morbidity, death, and socioeconomic impact, COPD is a serious global public health issue. Adeyoye et al. (10) estimated a global prevalence of 11.7 percent (8.4 percent to 15.0 percent) cases in 2010, corresponding to 384 million cases, in a systematic review and meta-analysis. The incidence varies depending on where you live. COPD is also anticipated to be the third leading cause of death on the globe by 2030 (11). COPD is also associated with a number of comorbidities, such as cardiovascular disease, osteoporosis, skeletal muscle wasting, anemia, and mental symptoms. Comorbidity diagnosis and therapy is critical in the management of this disease since comorbidities cause a reduction in quality of life, increasing the risk of hospitalization and mortality (12). Another concern with COPD is the under-diagnosis of the disease. According to data from the third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES III), roughly 63 percent of persons with lung function impairment have never been diagnosed with asthma or COPD (13).

The prognosis will be improved if a significant proportion of undiagnosed COPD patients are diagnosed in a timely manner. Other respiratory disorders, such as TB, have been related to an increased risk of COPD, and it has been observed that a history of TB can result in the development of COPD during therapy or, in some circumstances, following therapy (14). As a result, COPD is a complicated and varied illness. Despite the fact that FEV1 has been utilized in patient diagnosis and follow-up, it is not an appropriate metric for disease monitoring (15). There is already a profusion of material accessible on several biomarkers for COPD diagnosis. These include a variety of sputum and blood biomarkers, each of which has its own set of limitations (16). The discovery of a powerful biomarker in COPD patients appears to be of interest. RAGE (receptor for advanced glycation end products) has long been known to have a role in inflammatory disease signaling, including COPD. RAGE is a multiligand receptor of the immunoglobulin superfamily that binds to a variety of ligands (17). RAGE has

gotten a lot of attention since 1992 because of its function in illnesses such as chronic inflammation, tumor expansion, diabetic complications, and neuronal degeneration in Alzheimer's disease and multiple sclerosis (18). According to Wu et al. (19), formalin-fixed lung tissue from COPD patients who had lobectomy for bronchial cancer exhibits considerably elevated RAGE staining. Alveolar walls showed elevated staining, but not the airways (19). As a result, the focus of this research has been on RAGE's possible function in COPD and its potential use as a biomarker. The function of RAGE, the AGE-RAGE axis, the soluble form of RAGE (sRAGE), and RAGE genetics in COPD have all been discussed.

2. Structure, Types, and Ligands of RAGE

RAGE Structure and Types

Human RAGE is encoded by a gene found on chromosome 6p21 of the Class III major histocompatibility complex (MHC) (20). RAGE is a 404-amino-acid multiligand trans-membrane protein with a 35-kD size and three primary regions: extracellular, trans-membrane, and cytoplasmic. The extracellular region, which is 22 amino acids away from the signaling area on the N terminal, is made up of a single variable (V) domain and two constant domains (C1 and C2), which are similar to the variable and constant portions of an immunoglobulin. The 21-amino-acid trans-membrane region aids in RAGE's anchoring to the cellular membrane, whereas the 41-amino-acid-long cytosolic tail aids in signal transmission (20). RAGE's cytoplasmic region has no resemblance to any known signaling domain. RAGE's three-dimensional crystal and solution structures demonstrate that the Variable 1 (V1) and Constant 1 (C1) domains work together to produce a compact unit with a broad cationic surface that aids in the binding of RAGE ligands (21).

The RAGE gene has a binding site for activator protein 1 (AP1), specificity protein 1 (SP1), and many other transcription factors, including nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B), which is known to influence RAGE gene transcription (21). The polyadenylated 3'-untranslated region of RAGE mRNA has a site for microRNA (miRNA) miR-30, which suppresses its expression (22). RAGE has been found to be widely distributed in numerous cells and tissues, and it is produced in a constitutive manner through several stages of embryonic development. However, its expression is reduced in adulthood, and it has been observed that it increases with age, particularly in the lungs (23). N-truncated, dominant-negative, and soluble RAGE are the three isoforms of RAGE produced via alternative splicing or membrane-associated proteases. Due to the absence of the V domain, RAGE variants with N-truncated forms are unable to interact with ligands; dominant-negative RAGE lacks the cytosolic domain, and RAGE missing the trans-membrane domain is known as sRAGE. sRAGE in plasma prevents RAGE ligands from interacting, which aids in the suppression of RAGE signals in a variety of human disorders (24). By competing with cell surface RAGE for ligand binding, sRAGE aids in the neutralization of circulating ligands (25). The AGEs, their kinds, and the signaling cascades generated by their contact with receptors are depicted graphically (RAGE). Upper: Various exogenous sources of AGEs (tobacco, cigarette, and dietary AGEs); pro-inflammatory AGEs are mostly derived from dietary components. Upper right: CML, pentosidine, MG, and imidazolone are examples of well-studied AGEs. Lower middle: AGEs and their receptors converse (RAGE). RAGE is a 404-aa protein with three primary regions: the extracellular area (22 aa from the signaling area), the trans-membrane (21 aa long), and the cytosolic area (41 aa long). TIRAP and MyD88 bind to RAGE's cytoplasmic domain and trigger downstream signaling pathways. Lower left: Other RAGE ligands (HMGB1, Mac1, S-100 proteins, -amyloid, -sheet fibrils, LPS, HSP70, C3a, and CpG DNA oligos) because it recognizes three-dimensional structures of the ligands rather than individual aa. Lower right:

Signaling downstream of the AGE-RAGE interaction, which leads to disease development. TIRAP, Toll-interleukin-1 receptor adapter protein; MyD88, myeloid differentiation main response 88; Mac1, macrophage-antigen-1; S-100 proteins, -amyloid, -sheet fibrils; LPS, lipopolysaccharides; HSP70, heat shock protein 70)

3. Image in its entirety

The Role of RAGE Ligands in COPD

RAGE, a multiligand receptor with the ability to recognize three-dimensional structures of ligands rather than a single amino acid, is also known as a pattern recognition receptor (PRR) (26). RAGE expression and levels of its ligands have been found to be elevated in the lungs, suggesting that RAGE signaling may play a role in COPD (27). Advanced glycation end products (AGEs), lipopolysaccharides, high mobility group box protein 1 (HMGB1), heat shock protein (HSP70), macrophage-antigen-1 (Mac1), S-100 proteins, -amyloid, C3a, and CpG DNA oligos are just a few examples of traditional and emerging RAGE ligands that can speed up signaling arrays depending on their type and nature (28). Various ligands generated by cigarette smoke (CS) are also recognized by RAGE (3).

AGEs are a broad set of highly oxidant and irreversibly produced chemicals that result from the non-enzymatic glycooxidation (Maillard reaction) of lipids, nucleic acids, and proteins (29). Peroxidation of lipids also results in the development of AGEs, which are also known as advanced lipoxidation end products (ALEs). The earliest RAGE ligands were AGEs, which are N-carboxymethyllysine-modified proteins (30). N-carboxy methyl-lysine (CML) and methylglyoxal (MG) are two well-known products of glucose-lipid or glucose-protein interactions that serve as AGE indicators (31). Although AGEs are produced by the body during normal metabolism, high levels of AGEs in various bodily tissues and circulation may be harmful (32). Various heat treatments were utilized to improve the food's safety, taste, and bioavailability, resulting in the Maillard reaction and the development of AGEs (33). By activating NF- κ B, AGEs binding to RAGE cause inflammation. As a result, it's possible that AGEs have a role in the development of COPD through inflammation (19).

4. Ligands from Other Sources

HMGB1 is a hexadecim number that (Amphoterin)

HMGB1, also known as amphoterin, is a family of non-histone nuclear proteins with high electrophoretic mobility that comprises the HMGB, HMGN, and HMGA superfamilies (34). The 215-amino-acid protein has two DNA-binding domains, the A-box and B-box, as well as a highly conserved C-terminal tail that is found in almost all eukaryotic cells (35). The protein operates as a damage-associated molecular pattern molecule (DAMP) in its extracellular form, triggering an immunological response by activating different receptors, including AGE receptors (36). HMGB1's COOH-terminal region aids its interaction with RAGE. Asthma and COPD patients have higher HMGB1 levels, which can be exploited as a target molecule in a variety of disorders (37). By interacting with RAGE and triggering upregulation of the RAGE signal, it can create a positive feedback loop (38). Furthermore, when HMGB1 and RAGE interact, the NF- κ B pathway is activated, causing inflammation to persist. Targeting NF- κ B with an inhibitor leads to the downregulation of HMGB1 in the lung tissue, according to research on mice with COPD (39).

Macrophage-Antigen-1 is a protein that is found on the surface of macrophages (Mac 1)

Macrophage Ag 1 (Mac-1) is a beta 2 integrin that is found on monocytes, neutrophils, and macrophages and is involved in adhesion, motility, phagocytosis, and chemotaxis (40). Mac-1, also known as M2, is made up of two non-covalently linked 165kD and 95kD subunits termed CD11b or M and CD18 or 2 (165 kD) and CD18 or 2 (95 kD) respectively (95 kD). Mac-1 has also been linked to an oxidative burst in neutrophils, the activation of a phagocytic oxidase (PHOX), and the stimulation of the NF- κ B signaling pathway (41). The presence of RAGE on neutrophils rather than endothelial cells is required for Mac-1-associated neutrophil recruitment triggered by HMGB1 (42). RAGE interacts with Mac-1's ligand-binding I-domain, and the resulting complex attracts leukocytes (43). Endothelial RAGE binds Mac-1 and intercellular adhesion molecule 1 (ICAM-1) for the recruitment of leukocytes in the tissue, according to a subsequent study (44). The knowledge of such interactions might be useful in the development of RAGE for novel therapeutic uses.

5. Proteins S-100

The biggest calcium-binding proteins of the EF-hand (helix E-loop-helix F) type, S100 proteins have a modest molecular weight ranging from 9 to 13 kDa. It is made up of 25 different components with significant structural homology (45). These regulate cellular proliferation, cell differentiation, cell death, Ca²⁺ homeostasis, metabolic responses, and numerous inflammatory responses. RAGE is involved in the majority of these processes (46). Furthermore, three S100 proteins (S100A8, S100A9, and S100A12) have been shown to increase the expression of Mucin 5AC (MUC5AC), a key mucin in conducting airways, and excessive MUC5AC production is one of the recognized important variables in obstructive airway pathophysiological processes (47). The binding of S100 proteins to TLR4 and RAGE receptors appears to trigger the synthesis of MUC5AC. Furthermore, RAGE could not be triggered by S100A8 and S100A9, according to the same study. Blocking S100A12 binding to RAGE had a selective effect on extracellular signal related (ERK) activation rather than NF- κ B activation, demonstrating a more flexible connection between these S100 proteins (47). This investigation discovered a link between prolonged neutrophilic inflammation and enhanced mucin formation in airway illness (47). S100B is expressed in numerous nervous system cells and has been linked to respiratory illnesses; increased levels of S100B have been identified in COPD patients, suggesting that it might be employed as a biomarker for brain damage in COPD patients (48).

6. β -Amyloid and β -Sheet Fibrils

The amyloid-beta (A) peptide is a 4 kDa peptide generated from the larger-amyloid precursor protein (APP) and was originally identified as the major ingredient of amyloid deposits in the brain of Alzheimer's disease (AD) patients, Down's syndrome individuals, and others (49). RAGE and amyloid-beta (A) interaction in brain endothelial cells produces signal molecules that lead to monocyte trafficking across the blood-brain barrier (BBB), and RAGE also mediates A transportation over the BBB, which leads to amyloid peptide buildup in the brain (50). RAGE has been linked to-amyloid in intracellular pathways and neurodegenerative illnesses such as Alzheimer's disease in several studies. In a study examining the relationship between COPD and dementia, Liao et al. (51) found that patients with COPD and dementia have a higher rate of hospital mortality and severe sepsis than those without dementia. Furthermore, a Chinese investigation found a substantial rise in blood A levels in cognitively normal COPD people when compared to the control group, suggesting that AD-related pathology alterations might be noticed in cognitively normal COPD patients (52). In the event of hypoxia and respiratory infections, increased A fibril deposition in COPD lungs, elevated serum levels, and impaired clearance from the brain have been documented (53).

7. Lipopolysaccharides are a kind of polysaccharide.

In a wide range of eukaryotic species, bacterial lipopolysaccharides (LPS) are potent inducers of innate immunity, with the lipid A component serving as the most significant immunostimulatory center (54). LPS, in combination with lipid A, has direct contact with RAGE, resulting in the stimulation of Tumour Necrosis Factor (TNF-) production and NF- κ B activation (28). The RAGE/NF- κ B signaling pathway was found to have a function in inflammatory lung damage generated by LPS in a newborn rat model of acute lung damage (55). RAGE also plays a role in the activation of NF- κ B, which is activated by LPS and endothelial hyperpermeability (56). Various RAGE ligands, including LPS, alter key biological processes involved in macrophage activation in a variety of illnesses and can be exploited as a biomarker.

8. Heat Shock Protein (HSP70)

HSP70 is a heat shock protein that participates in de novo protein folding and refolding and is recognized by a variety of plasma membrane receptors, including TLR4, TLR 2, cluster of differentiation 14 (CD), and CD40 (57). This connection promotes NF- κ B signaling, resulting in the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines and aiding immune cell phagocytic activity (57). HSP70 interacts with RAGE, along with other ligands, according to studies, and this ligation activates several signaling pathways (58). HSP70 expression in peripheral lung tissue increases in COPD and is exacerbated by cigarette smoking, and it is subsequently linked to COPD severity and IL-8 levels (59). Furthermore, plasma HSP70 levels were greater in a case-control research on coal miners including HSP70 and HSP27, but plasma HSP27 levels were lower (60). The necrotic lung cells may possibly be the source of increased plasma HSP70, according to the research (60).

9. Axis of AGE-RAGE

AGEs can be found in a variety of places.

Endogenous and external factors both contribute to the production of AGEs. Endogenous AGEs are formed by the dietary consumption of carbohydrates, mostly fructose, and the oxidation of fatty acids and glucose. Exogenous AGEs are produced by a variety of food processing procedures that employ heat, as well as cigarette smoking (61). Excessive consumption of dietary AGEs has been linked to inflammation and oxidative stress, which can contribute to the development of a variety of disorders.

10. Signaling in the AGE-RAGE Interaction Downstream

When RAGE binds to its ligands, it activates a number of signaling pathways. These pathways are dependent on the kind of ligand, the milieu of cells, and the milieu of tissues; hence, RAGE ligand binding mediates a wide range of cellular responses (58). According to many structural and biochemical investigations, there is a preassembly of RAGE in the plasma membrane in the absence of ligands, and when the ligands are bound, RAGE dimerizes, which is necessary for the commencement of RAGE signal transduction (62). AGEs, cellular receptor RAGE, sRAGE, and endogenous secretory RAGE (esRAGE) are four important components in the AGE-RAGE axis (63). The intracellular domain of RAGE is required for NF- κ B activation and downstream signaling (63). Ras-ERK1/2, NADPH oxidase, stress-activated protein kinase/jun amino-terminal kinases, Ras, Src kinase, and p38 MAPK pathways, as well as PI3K/Akt, small GTPase Cdc42/Rac, RhoA-associated kinase, protein kinase C beta II, and glycogensynthase kin The interaction of AGE and RAGE on the plasma membrane has a negative impact on cellular functioning. In neurons, endothelial cells, lung

cells, and muscle cells, it stimulates NF- κ B, activator protein 1, cyclic AMP response element-binding (CREB) protein, early growth response-1 (EGR-1), signal transducers and activators of transcription 3 (STAT3), and apoptosis (58, 64). Several intracellular adaptor proteins, including Toll-Interleukin-1 receptor adapter protein (TIRAP) and Myeloid differentiation primary response 88 (MyD88), have been shown to trigger downstream signaling cascades by interacting with RAGE's cytoplasmic domain (58). There is no indication that the RAGE cytoplasmic domain activates downstream signaling cascades in any way. AGE/RAGE signaling has a variety of impacts on different types of cells. Apoptosis, oxidative stress, autophagy, inflammatory responses, and transition of endothelial-mesenchymal cells are all modulated by AGE-RAGE signaling in endothelial cells, while the interaction promotes the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), proliferation, and calcification in smooth muscle cells (65). In lymphocytes and fibroblasts, AGE/RAGE signaling promotes proliferation, migration, inflammation, and death (65). When cells are exposed to AGE and LPS, activation of NF- κ B leads to IL-6 generation, according to a study conducted on the murine J774 macrophage cell line (66). Furthermore, AGE and LPS exposure causes RAGE and/or TLR4 signaling, which results in ROS generation. AGE/LPS has also been shown to need ROS to induce IL-6 production in J774 macrophages (66). As a result, the RAGE signaling pathway is important in a variety of human disorders, and its numerous stimulating stimuli can be exploited as therapeutic approaches or biomarkers for illness detection (20).

11. In COPD, the AGE-RAGE Axis and sRAGE play a role.

RAGE is a pro-inflammatory PRR, as previously mentioned, and different studies have identified RAGE as a key mediator of asthma, pulmonary fibrosis, allergic airway inflammation (AAI), lung cancer, COPD, and a variety of other disorders (27). RAGE expression and its different ligands are increased in the lungs, but sRAGE expression is decreased, indicating a role in COPD development (27). AGEs harm tissues in two ways: first, they modify protein structures by covalently cross-linking them, and second, they activate a number of intracellular pathways that increase the production of inflammatory cytokines and the creation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (23). Furthermore, AGEs-RAGE interaction inhibits TGF-mediated activation of ERK1/2 and SMAD, as well as upregulating Egr-1, which stimulates RAGE transcription in COPD (67). Chronic oxidative stress, which has also been linked to COPD, is the most important regulator of AGE production. The buildup of AGEs in the small airways and lung parenchyma of COPD patients has been documented (19). AGEs have also been found to be more prevalent in the skin of COPD patients than in the skin of healthy smokers and nonsmokers (68). Further research found no significant variations in skin autofluorescence (SAF) values between COPD severity stages, suggesting that AGE generation during disease progression is not enhanced but may be accelerated during the COPD induction phase (69). It has also been shown that AGEs accumulate to some extent as people age as a result of oxidative stress responses, and that this buildup is increased by smoking (69). Sanders and colleagues (3) found that deleting RAGE or inhibiting it inhibits the development of emphysema caused by cigarette smoke. The deletion of the RAGE gene affects the expression of a number of other important genes implicated in COPD development. They also discovered that RAGE null mice had less endoplasmic reticulum stress and oxidative damage, even when they were continuously exposed to cigarette smoke.

sRAGE acts as a decoy receptor, removing circulating AGEs and preventing them from attaching to membrane-bound RAGE, limiting lung tissue harm (70). Furthermore, sRAGE suppresses AGE-RAGE-dependent inflammatory cytokine production in mononuclear cells

while promoting the formation of alternatively activated macrophages and regulatory dendritic cells (DCs) (71). Morbini and colleagues (72) initially observed enhanced RAGE expression in the lungs of cigarette smokers with chronic bronchitis and emphysema in 2006, while Wu et al. (19) found higher RAGE expression in the alveolar walls and epithelia of COPD smokers' airways in 2011. The levels of AGEs and their receptors in bodily compartments such as bronchial biopsies, sputum, plasma, and skin were shown to be greater in the skin of COPD patients, but sRAGE levels were found to be lower, indicating that sRAGE has a protective effect on the skin (69). Furthermore, RAGE overexpression causes a rise in nitric oxide (NO) levels and NO synthase activity in COPD smokers, as well as a drop in total glutathione levels, which increases NF- κ B activation (73).

Reduced levels of sRAGE were shown to be strongly linked to the impairment of diffusing lung capacity and the amount of structural emphysema in a case-control study on COPD (74). Nonsmokers, smokers without COPD, and smokers with COPD had their plasma levels of sRAGE and HMGB1 tested, and it was discovered that smokers with and without COPD had significantly lower sRAGE plasma levels than nonsmokers (75). From the explanation above, it is obvious that RAGE expression is raised in COPD, but sRAGE expression is lowered. The balance of RAGE and sRAGE might be a pathogenic factor or biomarker in COPD (76). The TESRA (Treatment of Emphysema with a Selective Retinoid Agonist) and ECLIPSE (Evaluation of COPD Longitudinally to Identify Predictive Surrogate Endpoints) cohorts found a link between sRAGE and several COPD clinical characteristics.

To begin with, sRAGE was a marker for the presence of emphysema. Lower levels of sRAGE were shown to be a biomarker of lung diffusing capacity for carbon monoxide (DLCO) and lung density in the TESRA cohort, whereas lower levels of sRAGE were linked with emphysema, GOLD stage, and COPD status in the ECLIPSE cohort. The relationships remained significant even after adjusting for covariates (77). According to Szewczyk et al. (78), sRAGE might be utilized to assist identify the frequent exacerbator phenotype and predict COPD exacerbations (ECOPD). There is less consensus on the effect of smoking on circulating sRAGE levels. Several investigations have found that there are no significant changes in blood sRAGE levels between smokers and non-smokers (79). The inconsistency of the sRAGE level owing to cigarette smoking was discussed by Prasad et al. (80). Smoking, on the other hand, causes a quick and substantial drop in serum sRAGE, according to research (81). Furthermore, smoking has been shown to have an immediate and transient influence on serum sRAGE (81). Because the results of these studies are inconsistent, various authors have reported and suggested that more research is needed before sRAGE can be considered a potential biomarker for COPD (82). More studies are needed to determine the consistency in serum sRAGE levels as a result of smoking among various groups to elucidate the acute and chronic effects of the same, and to make it a stable biomarker.

12. Other Biomarkers for COPD

Inhalation of tobacco or other toxic gases triggers the pulmonary inflammatory cascade, which includes many types of cells and inflammatory mediators such as C-reactive protein (CRP), fibrinogen, tumor necrosis factor- α , and many interleukins, all of which cause tissue injury and alter the structure of the airways (83). Although the FEV1 lung function test is the most common way to track COPD development, additional circulating biomarkers in COPD patients' peripheral blood can also be used to determine disease severity. Several studies have analyzed several COPD biomarkers, such as the existence of the illness, various phenotypes, and therapy response. Reduced clara cell secretory protein-16 (CC-16) and

sRAGE are linked to emphysema, whereas increased C-reactive protein (CRP), fibrinogen, leucocyte count, and interleukins are linked to COPD exacerbations and death (84).

Hurst and colleagues (85) looked at 36 biomarkers for the diagnosis and treatment of COPD, which are included in Table 1. They also looked at CRP, which is a pentameric acute phase reactant protein generated by the liver and generated predominantly by IL-6, the amount of which rises in response to inflammation. CRP levels were elevated in patients with moderate to severe COPD, regardless of cigarette use, according to Plata and colleagues (86). In a comprehensive review and meta-analysis, Fermont and colleagues found a link between CRP and severe COPD clinical outcomes (87). Another research found a link between CRP and fibrinogen and an increased risk of mortality in COPD patients (88). Fibrinogen is an acute phase protein (340 kDa homodimeric glycoprotein) that is largely generated in hepatocytes and circulates at a concentration of 2-5 mg/mL in healthy people (89). The most promising COPD measure is plasma fibrinogen, which is the only FDA-approved blood-based drug development biomarker for patients with a high mortality risk (90). Fibrinogen has been linked to the severity of COPD, but no reduction in lung function has been detected. Oral corticosteroids lower fibrinogen during COPD exacerbations, while p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase inhibitors diminish it in those with stable illness (91). Another research (92) discovered a link between high fibrinogen levels and an increased risk of COPD. IL-6, IL-8, and tumor necrosis factor are also key COPD indicators. T cells, monocytes, fibroblasts, and endothelial cells generate IL-6, a pleiotropic cytokine that aids in the regulation of immunological and inflammatory responses. IL-6 promotes the production of hepatic acute phase protein, which contributes to a decline in health. Sputum, bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL), and concentrated exhaled air from COPD patients had higher amounts of IL-6 (93). In research done by Moraes et al. (83), individuals with COPD had higher blood levels of IL-6 and IL-8 than those in the control group. Higher levels of IL-6 were detected in individuals with a BMI of less than 21 kg/m² who also had a high smoking load and bronchitis, while IL-8 was only observed in the group with the most COPD exacerbations.

13. COPD and RAGE Genetics

In the etiology of airway illnesses, including asthma and COPD, interactions between genes and the environment are crucial (94, 95). Several genes have been identified as being relevant to COPD (96). Early research on the role of genetics in COPD showed that Alpha-1-antitrypsin (AAT) deficiency is a genetic risk factor, and it is still the only genetic subtype with a particular therapy (97). Several Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS) on lung function and airway obstruction illnesses have now shown a number of genetic loci linked to these conditions. In 2009, Pillai et al. (98) conducted the first COPD GWAS in a case-control cohort, finding a substantial relationship between 15q25 region/CHRNA3/CHRNA5/IREB2 and COPD. Cho et al. (99,100,101) conducted three GWASs in 2010, 2012, and 2014, identifying additional genetic loci such as 4q22 areas FAM13A, 1q41, TGFB2, and HHIP covering the 4q31 region linked to COPD. Cho et al. (101) incorporated the ECLIPSE, National Emphysema Treatment Trial/Normative Aging Study (NETT/NAS), and GenKOLS data with genome-wide association analysis that covered all moderate to severe cases in their GWAS done in 2014. They validated the linkage of a new locus 14q32 near RIN3 with the previously identified loci. Following that, GWAS on COPD undertaken by Chen et al. (102), Hobbs et al. (103), and Burkart et al. (104) identified additional loci that are genome-wide significant and linked to COPD. The GWAS loci that have been reported are being examined and examined in order to learn more about the function of COPD genetics. In the case of other airway illnesses, such as asthma, potential gene variants were thoroughly investigated. The

strong connection of gene variations in the case of asthma has also been documented in population-based case-control studies (105). COPD genetics and the connection of numerous loci identified by population-based GWAS and meta-analysis studies have been highlighted in recent research (96, 106). Although GWAS found some important genetic areas related to COPD, alternative techniques are necessary to gain a more complete understanding of key genetic areas related to COPD due to the limitations of this research. Various sequencing-based and network-based techniques have recently revealed insights into COPD genetics (107). As previously reported, the *AGER* gene, which encodes RAGE and is located at 6p.21.3, is highly polymorphic and has been associated with the pathophysiology of COPD (108, 109). *AGER* expression is known to be induced by oxidative and inflammatory stressors. In comparison to other tissues, *AGER* is highly expressed in lung tissues, and its expression is increased in COPD due to the buildup of RAGE ligands (110, 111). Variants of the *AGER* gene have also been linked to a variety of additional disease outcomes (112). Initially, single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) of the *AGER* gene were linked to lung functions in a meta-analysis of significant population-based GWAS (113, 114). According to research published in 2009, 6p21 (*AGER*) is one of five unique genome-wide loci associated with pulmonary function. Furthermore, the study found a link between 6p21 and *FEV1/FEVC* in the Dishevelled Associated Activator Of Morphogenesis 2 (*DAAM2*) gene (113). In *AGER*, rs2070600 was also shown to be a sentinel SNP for *FEV1/FVC*. However, *AGER* was shown to be inconsequential in the case of COPD in a subsequent investigation, although it was shown to be strongly correlated with *FEV1/FVC* without a clear relation with *FEV1*. The disparities in these results have been attributed to a lack of statistical power (115).

Cloning and sequencing of *AGER*'s 5' flanking region revealed a single main transcriptional start point. The-1543/-587 region of *AGER* has been found to have a role in regulating promoter responsiveness. Two important NF- κ B sites were also discovered inside the promoter for the control of RAGE expression in different stages (116). sRAGE levels in COPD patients have been found to be low in several investigations. sRAGE levels were linked to airflow restriction, CT defined emphysema, and DLCO in a research including two well-characterized, independent, and large cohorts of COPD patients enrolled in TESRA and ECLIPSE (77). Furthermore, the *AGER* gene variations rs2071288 and rs2070600 were shown to be strongly linked to sRAGE levels. Due to the lack of data for rs2071288 for ECLIPSE analysis, it only exhibited interaction in TESRA with both DLCO and sRAGE levels. rs2070600 was shown to be associated with sRAGE levels in each of these cohorts (77). A case-control study in 216 Chinese patients was done to determine the relation of three *AGER* variants, 374T/A, 429T/C, and G82S, with COPD. Of the three, only G82S of the protein product of *AGER* is linked with COPD. They found that G82S leads to COPD development and that the GS genotype is a larger risk factor among smokers (108). Guo et al. (117) also found a link between rs2070600 and COPD in a case-control study of the Chinese Han population. Later, Miller et al. (109) used allele-specific RAGE cell models to examine UK smokers and found that rs2070600 (G82S) changes the ligand-dependent release of sRAGE in the airways. The rs2070600T genotype, which corresponds to serine82, protects smokers in the United Kingdom against COPD by demonstrating improved lung function and lower serum sRAGE levels. The *AGER* variant rs2070600 has been shown to be related to COPD in a variety of populations and has genome-wide relevance (103). Hall et al. (118) examined the genetics of COPD and asthma, using data from GWAS, meta-analyses, and other genetic research. The effect of *AGER* variation rs2070600 on pulmonary function and COPD was also described in the same research (118). Niu et al. (119) investigated the relation of *AGER* gene variations (rs1800625, rs1800624, rs2070600, rs184003, and rs2071288) with

COPD and asthma in the northern Han Chinese population. A promoter variation, rs1800625, -429T > C, was shown to be linked to the risk of COPD in the population investigated. However, the results of this investigation differ from those of prior research done by Li et al. (108) in the southern Chinese population, in which rs1800625 showed no significant correlation while G82S did. Climate and cultural variances among the people have been blamed for the inconsistencies (119). In addition to the variations, the influence of the AGER splicing process has been investigated. A recent research on the AGER gene looked at the expression of all of its splice sites in relation to overall gene expression in smokers and never smokers to determine the amount of alternative splicing in these individuals (120). The study found that, whereas overall AGER gene expression is lower in smokers, the component of AGER related to the synthesis of the anti-inflammatory esRAGE protein is higher (120). This revealed fresh information on the body's defensive molecular system against the negative effects of smoking.

14. Conclusion

Finally, through binding to many ligands, RAGE plays an important part in a variety of intracellular processes. RAGE ligand interactions activate downstream signaling pathways that have been linked to a variety of illnesses, including COPD. Furthermore, inhibitors of RAGE and its signaling pathways have been revealed to have a role in the pathophysiology of a variety of illnesses, suggesting that they might be utilized to treat COPD (121, 122). Due to a lack of reliable and consistent biomarkers, COPD is frequently misdiagnosed. RAGE, sRAGE, and several of its ligands have been discovered to be changed in COPD patients. sRAGE is still a proposed biomarker for COPD. However, due to a lack of agreement among studies on the influence of smoking on sRAGE levels, additional research is needed to determine whether or not it is a stable biomarker. A recent investigation into the northern Han Chinese population found that the promoter mutation -429T > C is linked to COPD (119). RAGE genetics is also emerging as a role in various groups' vulnerability to COPD. For a better diagnosis of the condition, more population-based research is needed. Finally, the AGE-RAGE axis, sRAGE, and RAGE genetics all play a role in COPD, and RAGE might be used as a biomarker for the diagnosis and management of COPD patients, depending on the results of future research (123-274).

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